

LIST OF REQUIREMENTS INCORPORATED INTO THE
NEW STANDARDS PRODUCED BY THE TEF
2024-12-24

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Abstract

The integration of AI and robotics in the agrifood sector presents unique challenges due to the complexity of these technologies and the variability of agricultural environments. This deliverable addresses the regulatory and conformity assessment landscape for AI-based solutions in agrifood, focusing on the specific requirements and challenges faced by developers and suppliers. It examines critical areas such as environmental and biological variability, cost and accessibility, interoperability, data privacy, and end-user trust, proposing strategies to address these issues.

The document provides an overview of relevant regulatory frameworks, including the AI Act, Machine Regulation (MR), and Cybersecurity Act, mapping these to the agrifood sector's needs and highlighting gaps in current standards. Special attention is given to conformity assessment to obtain CE Marking, a key milestone for ensuring market readiness and compliance within the European Economic Area (EEA). The deliverable outlines the role of AgrifoodTEF in offering tailored services, including support for ethical data practices, field demonstrations, and seamless integration testing, to foster trust and adoption among stakeholders. It concludes with strategic recommendations for enhancing conformity assessment practices, thereby supporting the safe, efficient, and responsible deployment of AI and robotics in the agrifood sector.

List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
EEA	European Economic Area
EMC	Electro-magnetic compatibility
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EUCC	European Union Common Criteria
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
LVD	Low Voltage Directive
MR	Machine Regulation
NLF	New Legislative Framework
RED	Radio Equipment Directive
TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facilities
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

AgrifoodTEF is a network of test and validation infrastructures in Europe that supports Agrifood technology companies to do near product development of their AI and Robotics solutions in real-world facilities. The overall aim is to close the gap between excellent research in these fields and actual products that support an efficient and sustainable agriculture, while meeting stringent usability and economic requirements of their end-users. AgrifoodTEF foundations are solidly rooted in existing experimental farms and facilities for AI and Robotics in Agriculture, already operational in various regions highly representative of European Agrifood production. They have been clustered to build scale and further enhance EU role in guaranteeing world food security with testing and validation facilities that will engage all relevant stakeholders with the best experts in the AI and Robotics technology domains. While each TEF-node will promote independent operations with a sustainable business model that will be optimized for the specialties and territorial needs, all TEF-nodes will share common guidelines, standards and support each other with services that can be offered across the different regions represented by nodes and satellites.

While other work packages (WP) of the project focus on physical and digital facilities for technical assessment of AI and Robotics solutions, mainly aiming at performance, quality and safety, WP 3 emphasizes aspects such as ethical, legal, societal, lifecycle, and cybersecurity assessments. These aspects are essential within the existing regulatory and standardization framework, particularly in the AI Act, the Machinery Regulation, the Data Act, and the Cybersecurity Act. The objective of WP 3 is to conduct a detailed analysis of the associated requirements and enable the project to offer a range of services that effectively address these aspects.

Particularly as the agrifood sector faces significant challenges in achieving regulatory compliance for AI and robotics solutions due to the inherent complexity of agricultural environments and the evolving nature of AI technologies. This deliverable explores these challenges and provides a comprehensive analysis of regulatory frameworks and best practices to support TEF partners in navigating fields of application of AgrifoodTEF's relevant standards and conformity assessment processes.

The deliverable also delves into key regulatory frameworks such as the AI Act, Machine Regulation, and Cybersecurity Act and others from the New Legislative Framework, emphasizing their relevance to the agrifood sector. CE Marking is highlighted as a critical step for market readiness, offering competitive advantages and fostering trust among stakeholders. The analysis identifies gaps in existing standards and comments on strategies for harmonization and future development.

AgrifoodTEF's role is to provide comprehensive support to clients, offering tools, infrastructures, and expertise to streamline compliance efforts. This deliverable serves as a roadmap for achieving regulatory alignment and optimizing market adoption of AI and robotics solutions in the agrifood sector, with actionable recommendations for stakeholders to address identified challenges and gaps.

1. Introduction

1.1. Agrifood challenges for AI and robotics conformity assessment

Despite a large number of existing standards, very few are adapted to AI products, and even fewer are harmonised with AgrifoodTEF relevant European regulations. In addition, the regulatory conformity assessment of AI and robotics solutions in the agrifood sector faces unique challenges due to the complexity of the technologies and their integration into agricultural practices.

Agrifood experts in the consortium have pointed the following challenges and issues for AI and robotics developers or suppliers: environmental and biological variability, cost and accessibility, interoperability and compatibility of emerging technologies in agrifood [1].

Agricultural environments are inherently variable, with factors like weather, soil type, pest infestations, and crop diversity differing across regions. AI and robotics must be tested under diverse and unpredictable conditions to ensure reliability. The agricultural cycle limits the availability of real-world testing windows, delaying conformity assessment processes when tests protocols relies on physical infrastructures such as experimentation and research farms [2]. This factor adds complexity to systems: they must demonstrate adaptability and effectiveness across a wide range of environmental and biological scenarios during conformity assessments [3]. AgrifoodTEF is studying the opportunities of using simulation testing to mimic diverse environmental conditions and reduce dependence on seasonal field trials.

Many agritech solutions need to be customized for local conditions (e.g., irrigation systems tailored to specific soil types or climates). This increases the difficulty of developing and certifying a universally compliant product and hence, certification processes may require multiple rounds of testing in different locations, leading to higher costs and longer timelines. AgrifoodTEF aims to build collaborations between TEF clients and regional farms to conduct real-world testing under specific environmental conditions.

Many agritech companies, especially smaller ones, focus on system development and often lack the financial or technical resources to navigate complex regulatory landscapes (and cannot easily absorb compliance costs). To face this issue, AgrifoodTEF provides services that help company understand and implement their conformity assessment roadmap (such as those described in Section 3.2). Although AI products certification and compliance to the AI Act are still very premature and inaccessible for high-risk AI products or components, WP3 services allows to comply with some requirements and anticipate future harmonised standards with the best tools and infrastructures available among TEF partners.

Agritech companies often develop solutions that must interface with existing equipment, sensors, or farm management software. They may also use a mix of old and new technologies, requiring solutions to be backward compatible. Ensuring seamless system integration and interoperability while meeting regulatory requirements is a significant technical challenge as farmers demand solutions that work with their existing systems. AgrifoodTEF diversity of partners provide access to a very important community and farm management platforms to test seamless integration. Conducted rigorously, these tests with real-world settings allows to identify and resolve compatibility issues before product launch.

Furthermore, ensuring that devices can communicate effectively, especially in IoT-connected farms, requires adherence to specific data and communication standards. Companies may face additional testing and certification

costs to ensure compatibility with third-party products and platforms. One solution could be to use widely adopted communication protocols and interoperability standards to reduce compatibility issues.

TEF clients end-users, namely farmers, may distrust AI systems, fearing they lack transparency or control over decision-making. Similarly, consumers may worry about food safety or ethical issues associated with robotics and AI. Thus, farmers may hesitate to adopt AI-driver solutions if liability for failures or damages caused by these systems is unclear. They are also concerned about data privacy and ownership that could deter farmers from sharing the data necessary for AI systems to function effectively.

Hence, building trust is essential for market adoption. Without clear communication about the benefits and safety of AI and robotics, farmers and consumers may resist these technologies. Some WP3 services help company clarify their technical documentation (how AI system works, safety measures, benefits for farmers and consumers), test their ethical data practices like their data privacy measures, and conduct (and communicate about) field demonstrations to show farmers the practical benefits and reliability of these technologies.

By addressing these challenges, regulators and industry stakeholders can foster safe, efficient, responsible integration, and optimize market adoption of AI and robotics into the agrifood sector.

1.2. Navigating AI regulatory landscapes in agrifood

This deliverable provides significant value by helping project partners navigate the complex regulatory landscape for AI-based solutions in the agrifood sector. By breaking down regulatory frameworks into major families of requirements and identifying existing resources such as standards and technical guides, it enables partners to focus on specific thematic areas. This structure supports the development of tailored service offerings that align with relevant norms and compliance expectations, fostering both market readiness and innovation.

CE Marking, as a key indicator of compliance with EU regulations, demonstrates that a product meets essential requirements for safety, health, and environmental protection. For AI systems in the agrifood sector, achieving CE Marking is a significant milestone, ensuring that solutions are fit for purpose and legally marketable across the European Economic Area (EEA). This mark not only signifies compliance but also fosters trust among stakeholders, including manufacturers, end-users, and regulatory authorities, by aligning products with high standards.

Compliance with EU regulations offers numerous advantages. Products bearing the CE Mark can be freely marketed within the EEA, facilitating trade and business expansion. It also ensures adherence to stringent safety and performance standards, minimizing risks of legal liabilities and recalls. By building confidence among consumers and partners, compliance enhances the reputation of solution providers, offering a competitive edge. Furthermore, adhering to these regulatory frameworks encourages robust design and development processes, fostering innovation that aligns with market and societal needs.

Despite its significance, achieving CE Marking for AI systems presents challenges. The dynamic nature of AI technology often outpaces the development of precise regulatory standards, leaving ambiguities in assessment criteria. Ensuring seamless integration of AI systems with existing processes and hardware can further complicate conformity assessments. Additionally, many AI systems lack sufficient mechanisms to demonstrate transparency, explainability, and accountability, which are key aspects under EU regulations like the AI Act. Robust mechanisms to address vulnerabilities and ensure secure operations are often underdeveloped, adding to the complexity of achieving conformity.

Within this context, the New Legislative Framework (NLF) emerges as a comprehensive structure to enhance market regulation within the EU. Its objectives include simplifying and strengthening processes for placing products on the market while ensuring a high level of protection for public interests such as safety, health, and the environment. The NLF encompasses several key directives and regulations, such as the Machine Regulation (MR) 2023/1230, which forms an integral part of this framework. These rules clarify the obligations for economic operators, including manufacturers, importers, and distributors, while ensuring coherence across regulatory frameworks. This reduces administrative burdens and enhances enforcement through market surveillance and consistent conformity assessment practices.

It is important to note that the AI Act, while a critical regulatory instrument for AI systems, is not formally part of the NLF. Instead, it operates as a distinct framework tailored to address the specific challenges and risks associated with AI technologies. Although the AI Act and the NLF share common goals, such as ensuring safety, transparency, and accountability, they remain separate but complementary in their regulatory scope.

This deliverable is structured to provide a clear roadmap for achieving compliance in the agrifood domain. It begins with a detailed review of existing regulatory frameworks, including the AI Act, Machine Regulation, Cybersecurity Act, and others, highlighting their relevance to AI in the agrifood sector. Following this, specific challenges in the agrifood sector are identified alongside recent perspectives on harmonized legal bases for European food safety control. The involvement of TEF partners in conformity assessment services is then explored, with insights from surveys and case studies of best practices among the partners. Finally, the conclusion synthesizes key insights and presents strategic recommendations to address gaps and enhance conformity assessment practices.

2. Overview of regulatory requirements

This chapter summarizes the European regulation analysis conducted in WP3 workshops to get a deeper understanding of key properties that will be defined in future standards, including harmonised standards. It relates of several EU regulations: the AI Act, the Cybersecurity Act and the related Common Criteria proposed in the EUCC, the Data Act and the Data Governance Act, and also several New Legislative Framework regulations such as the Machinery Regulation, the EMC Directive, the LVD Directive and the RED Directive.

In the following tables, the extraction of all the key attributes in the selected EU regulation articles allows us to draw a matching table between key attributes and existing or future related standards that may provide technical specification of the necessary requirements needed to comply with EU regulations. The standards related to these regulations and to agrifood AI and robotics systems are listed in the deliverable D3.1.

The main objective of these tables is to point out attributes currently covered by standards and that could be added as new conformity assessment services. It also indicates what are attributes and requirements not yet covered into recent standards.

Note: the full titles of the standards cited in the tables below are presented in the Section 5, with links when available.

2.1. AI Act 2024/1689

The AI Act represents a pioneering regulatory framework specifically addressing the unique challenges and risks posed by artificial intelligence systems within the European Union. While the Act sets out stringent requirements for transparency, robustness, fairness, and accountability, the development of harmonized standards to support these requirements is still underway. In the interim, guidance is provided through related standards that align with the spirit of the AI Act’s principles. However, these preliminary standards do not grant a presumption of conformity and may not fully cover the scope of the Act’s requirements. This creates a transitional period where compliance efforts rely on approximations that, while useful, require ongoing refinement to achieve comprehensive alignment with the AI Act’s expectations.

Table 1. AI Act 2024/1689 attributes and related standards

AI Act 2024/1689: Chapter III - High-risks system			
Article		Attributes to evaluate	(Present/future) Potential standards for conformity assessment
SECTION 2: REQUIREMENTS FOR HIGH-RISK AI SYSTEMS	Article 9 Risk management system	Documentation Risk identification, evaluation, monitoring, elimination/reduction and management Provision of information Training, testing Real-world conditions Metric Probabilistic threshold AI impact Vulnerable groups	ISO 42001 LNE Certification of AI processes ELSA scans ISO/IEC TR 29119-11 EN ISO/IEC 23894 FprCEN/CLC/TR 18145

	<p>Article 10 Data and data governance</p>	<p>Training dataset Validation dataset Testing dataset Data collection process Annotation Data preparation Data qualification Biases analysis Biases mitigation Data shortcomings Representativity Data features Biases detection Data securisation Pseudonymisation Privacy measures Personnal data management</p>	<p>GDPR Certification CEN/CLC/TR 18115 FprCEN/CLC/TR 18145 prEN ISO/IEC 5259-2</p>
	<p>Article 11 Technical documentation</p>	<p>Conformity assessment Technical documentation Event recording</p>	<p>ISO 17025</p>
	<p>Article 12 Record-keeping</p>	<p>Logging capabilities traceability Monitoring Period recording Reference dataset Input data Result verification Person identification</p>	<p>ISO/IEC TR 29119-11 CEN/CLC/TR 18115</p>

	<p>Article 13 Transparency and provision of information to deployers</p>	<p>Compliance Transparency Interpretability System output Technical documentation User instruction Robustness Metrics Accuracy Testing Risk assessment Performance assessment Explainability Input specifications Output specifications Monitoring Logging capabilities Human oversight management Hardware resources Software resources Life-cycle management</p>	<p>ISO/IEC 25010 ISO 18497 ISO/IEC TR 29119-11 EN 16524 FprCEN/CLC/TR 18145</p>
	<p>Article 14 Human oversight</p>	<p>Human-machine interface description Human oversight measures and management Risk mitigation Technical documentation Anomalies management Automation bias management Interpretability Output specification AI system usability AI system operation AI system interruption</p>	<p>ISO/IEC CD 42015</p>

	<p>Article 15 Accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity</p>	<p>Accuracy Robustness Cybersecurity Benchmark Measurement methodologies Metrics User documentation Resilience Bias management Bias mitigation Errors management Vulnerabilities management Risk management Attacks management Data poisoning Model poisoning Adversarial attacks Model evasion Confidentiality attacks</p>	<p>CEN/CLC/TR 18115 FprCEN/CLC/TR 18145 prEN ISO/IEC 5259-2 ISO/IEC/TR 24029</p>
<p>SECTION 3: OBLIGATIONS OF PROVIDERS AND DEPLOYERS OF HIGH-RISK AI SYSTEMS AND OTHER PARTIES</p>	<p>Article 16 Obligations of providers of high-risk AI systems</p>	<p>Conformity Contact information Quality management system Documentation management Logs management Monitoring</p>	<p>CEN/CLC/TR 17894</p>
	<p>Article 17 Quality management system</p>	<p>Quality management system Documentation management Transparency Design control Technical specifications Data management Risk management Maintenance Monitoring Communication Record-keeping management Resource management Design verification Testing procedures Validation procedures Traceability Quality control Quality assurance Quality management system</p>	<p>ISO 42001 CEN/CLC/TR 17894 ISO/IEC 25059</p>

	Article 18 Documentation keeping	Documentation management Technical documentation Quality management system Approved changes Notified bodies Conformity declaration	ISO/IEC 25010
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2.2. New Legislative Framework for Machines

2.2.1. Machine Regulation (MR) 2023/1230

The Machine Regulation (MR) 2023/1230 is a cornerstone of the NLF designed to ensure the safety and compliance of machinery within the European Union. It replaces the previous Machinery Directive 2006/42/EC and introduces updated provisions to address emerging technologies, including AI-driven systems, robotics, and connected devices. The regulation sets out clear requirements for manufacturers, importers, and distributors, focusing on essential health and safety considerations. It also emphasizes the need for robust risk assessments and conformity procedures to ensure that machinery placed on the market is safe, reliable, and environmentally friendly. The MR facilitates harmonization across member states, supporting the free movement of goods while maintaining high safety standards for users and operators.

Table 2. Machine Regulation 2023/1230 attributes and related standards

Machine Regulation 2023/1230			
Article	Attributes to evaluate		(Present/future) Potential standards for conformity assessment
BEFORE THE MAIN BODY OF THE ACT	(11)	Technical documentation Product prototype Transparency Ergonomy UX design	ISO 12100 ISO/TS 15066 ISO 13850 ISO 14118 ISO 13851 EN ISO 15641 EN 16524
	(15)	Typology assessment of machine: machine, connex product or quasi-machine Risk analysis	ISO 12100 ISO/TS 15066

ANNEX 3: ESSENTIAL HEALTH AND SAFETY REQUIREMENTS RELATING TO THE DESIGN AND	(25)	Other risks related to new digital technologies and mitigations	ISO 12100 ISO/TS 15066 ISO 4254 ISO 17989 ISO 20966 EN ISO 15641 EN ISO 16119 EN 16524 ISO/FDIS 3991
	(28)	Protection of the health and safety of [...] consumers, professional users, domestic animals, property, environment and fair competition on the Union market	EN ISO 16119 EN 16524
	(32)	Risk assessment within the scope of the market Health and safety requirements applicable to the product Future updates or developments of software [...] during the product's lifecycle due to an intended evolution of its behaviour to operate with varying levels of autonomy	ISO 17989 ISO/PWI 18460
	(33)	Dependencies and interactions between its components Risk assessment	/
	(34)	Technical documentation of detailed plans of subassemblies	/
	(36)	Compliance of third country products entering EU Ownership Liability	CEN/SS F05
	(54)	Conformity assessment of a safety component carried out by a third party	CEN/SS F05
	(59)	Responsability of conformity assessment	/
		1.1.9 Protection against corruption	Cybersecurity Access logging Pen tests Safety measures against accidental or intentional corruption

	1.2.1 Safety and reliability of control systems	Safety Operational Design Domain Edge-cases	ISO 18497 ISO 19206-2 IEC 62061 ISO 17989 ISO 15926-13 EN ISO 15641
	1.2.2 Control devices	Safety tests Perception tests For autonomous systems, surrounding pedestrian detection before starting	ISO 18497 ISO 19206-2 NF EN IEC 62046 EN ISO 13855 ISO/PWI 18460
	3.2.4 Supervisory function	Safety tests Remote sensing	ISO 19206-2 ISO 13849 IEC 62061 ISO 20966 EN ISO 13855 CLC IEC/TR 61508
	3.3.3 Travelling function	Safety tests Risk analysis Emergency button: response time, failure modes Testing situations: driver failure, system failure	ISO 13849 ISO 13850 ISO 14118 NF EN 60204 ISO 13851 ISO 25119
	3.5.1 Batteries	Testing situation: autonomous navigation to a charging station Perception test: contact or collision of the machinery with a person or other machinery	ISO 18497 ISO 19206-2 NF EN IEC 62046 EN ISO 13855 ISO/PWI 18460
	3.6.3.3 Autonomous mobile machinery or related products	Characteristics of its intended travel, working areas and danger zones	ISO 18497 ISO 19206-2
ANNEX 4: TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION FOR MACHINERY AND RELATED PRODUCTS (PART B)	(m) & (n) Technical documentation for partly completed machinery	Transparency Technical documentation Safety tests Transparency Technical documentation including product limitations Product prototype	EN 16524

2.2.2. Electro Magnetic Compatibility Directive (EMC) 2014/30/UE

The EMC directive 2014/30/EU is based on the NLF decision (EU) 768/2008. This means that it only contains essential requirements (in other words, general requirements) and the detailed technical requirements are transferred to standards harmonised with the directive. Harmonised standards, when cited in the Official Journal of the European Union, provide a legally-binding “presumption of conformity”. This means that such standards are recognized in Europe as providing state-of-the-art technical specifications allowing demonstration of compliance with the essential requirements of the directive, i.e. electromagnetic emissions and immunity of apparatus and installations in the context of the directive.

The table below lists a set of major standards. The exhaustive list of harmonized standards is available at <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/51315>.

Table 3. EMC Directive - 2014/30/UE attributes and related standards

EMC Directive - 2014/30/UE			
Article (only relevant one to AgrifoodTEF)	Attributes to evaluate	(Present/future) Potential standards for conformity assessment	
THE MAIN BODY OF THE LEGAL ACT	Article 6 Essential requirements	Conformity Electromagnetic compatibility Robotic machines	EN 61000-6-1, EN 61000-6-2, EN 61000-6-3, EN 61000-6-4, EN 55012, EN ISO 14982.
	Article 7 Obligations of manufacturers	Documentation	/
	Article 8 Authorised representatives	Documentation	/
	Article 9 Obligations of importers	Documentation	/
	Article 10 Obligations of distributors	Documentation	/
	Article 13 Presumption of conformity of equipment	Conformity Electromagnetic compatibility Robotic machines	EN 61000-6-1, EN 61000-6-2, EN 61000-6-3, EN 61000-6-4, EN 55012, EN ISO 14982.
	Article 14 Conformity assessment procedures for apparatus	Conformity Electromagnetic compatibility Robotic machines	EN 61000-6-1, EN 61000-6-2, EN 61000-6-3, EN 61000-6-4, EN 55012, EN ISO 14982.

	Article 15 EU declaration of conformity	Documentation	EN 61000-6-1, EN 61000-6-2, EN 61000-6-3, EN 61000-6-4, EN 55012, EN ISO 14982.
	Article 16 General principles of the CE marking	Documentation	/
	Article 17 Rules and conditions for affixing the CE marking	Documentation	/
	Article 19 Fixed installations	Conformity Electromagnetic compatibility Robotic machines	EN 61000-6-1, EN 61000-6-2, EN 61000-6-3, EN 61000-6-4, EN 55012, EN ISO 14982.
	Article 40 Formal non-compliance	Documentation	/
ANNEX I ESSENTIAL REQUIREMENTS	1. General requirement	Conformity Electromagnetic compatibility Robotic machines	EN 61000-6-1, EN 61000-6-2, EN 61000-6-3, EN 61000-6-4, EN 55012, EN ISO 14982
	2. Specific requirements for fixed installations	Conformity Electromagnetic compatibility Robotic machines	EN 61000-6-1, EN 61000-6-2, EN 61000-6-3, EN 61000-6-4, EN 55012, EN ISO 14982.
ANNEX IV EU DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY		Documentation	EN 61000-6-1, EN 61000-6-2, EN 61000-6-3, EN 61000-6-4, EN 55012, EN ISO 14982.

2.2.3. Low Voltage Directive (LVD) 2014/35/EU

The LVD Low Voltage Directive - 2014/35/EU is based on the NLF decision (EU) 768/2008. This means that it only contains essential requirements (in other words, general requirements) and the detailed technical requirements are transferred to standards harmonised with the directive. If harmonised standards do not exist, then the safety provisions of the international standards laid down by the International Electrotechnical Commission should be applied or national standards. In such a case the product will not benefit from presumption of conformity conferred by the use of such standards and the manufacturer must include all relevant information in the technical documentation. The essential requirements of the directive or in other words, elements of the safety objectives for electrical equipment designed for use within certain voltage limits, are:

1. General conditions

- (a) the essential characteristics, the recognition and observance of which will ensure that electrical equipment will be used safely and in applications for which it was made, shall be marked on the electrical equipment, or, if this is not possible, on an accompanying document;
- (b) the electrical equipment, together with its component parts, shall be made in such a way as to ensure that it can be safely and properly assembled and connected;
- (c) the electrical equipment shall be so designed and manufactured as to ensure that protection against the hazards set out in points 2 and 3 is assured, providing that the equipment is used in applications for which it was made and is adequately maintained.

2. Protection against hazards arising from the electrical equipment

Measures of a technical nature shall be laid down in accordance with point 1, in order to ensure that:

- (a) persons and domestic animals are adequately protected against the danger of physical injury or other harm which might be caused by direct or indirect contact;
- (b) temperatures, arcs or radiation which would cause a danger, are not produced;
- (c) persons, domestic animals and property are adequately protected against non-electrical dangers caused by the electrical equipment which are revealed by experience;
- (d) the insulation is suitable for foreseeable conditions.

3. Protection against hazards which may be caused by external influences on the electrical equipment
Technical measures shall be laid down in accordance with point 1, in order to ensure that the electrical equipment:

- (a) meets the expected mechanical requirements in such a way that persons, domestic animals and property are not endangered;
- (b) is resistant to non-mechanical influences in expected environmental conditions, in such a way that persons, domestic animals and property are not endangered;
- (c) does not endanger persons, domestic animals and property in foreseeable conditions of overload.

The full list of currently harmonised standards here: <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/62994>.

Table 4. LVD Low Voltage Directive - 2014/35/EU attributes and related standards

LVD Low Voltage Directive - 2014/35/EU			
Article (only relevant one to AgrifoodTEF)		Attributes to evaluate	(Present/future) Potential standards for conformity assessment
THE MAIN BODY OF THE ACT	Article 3 Making available on the market and safety objectives	Conformity Electrical safety Robotic machines	EN 60204-1, EN 60034-1, EN 60215, EN 60335-1, EN 60529, EN 60730-1, EN 60947-1, EN 61010-1, EN IEC 61204, EN IEC 61293.
	Article 6 Obligations of manufacturers	Documentation	/
	Article 7 Authorised representatives	Documentation	/

	Article 8 Obligations of importers	Documentation	/
	Article 9 Obligations of distributors	Documentation	/
	Article 12 Presumption of conformity on the basis of harmonised standards	Conformity Electrical safety Robotic machines	EN 60204-1, EN 60034-1, EN 60215, EN 60335-1, EN 60529, EN 60730-1, EN 60947-1, EN 61010-1, EN IEC 61204, EN IEC 61293.
	Article 13 Presumption of conformity on the basis of international standards	Conformity Electrical safety Robotic machines	/
	Article 14 Presumption of conformity on the basis of national standards	Conformity Electrical safety Robotic machines	/
	Article 15 EU declaration of conformity	Documentation	EN 60204-1, EN 60034-1, EN 60215, EN 60335-1, EN 60529, EN 60730-1, EN 60947-1, EN 61010-1, EN IEC 61204, EN IEC 61293.
	Article 16 General principles of the CE marking	Documentation	/
	Article 17 Rules and conditions for affixing the CE marking	Documentation	/
ANNEX I PRINCIPAL ELEMENTS OF THE SAFETY OBJECTIVES FOR ELECTRICAL		Conformity Electrical safety Robotic machines	EN 60204-1, EN 60034-1, EN 60215, EN 60335-1, EN 60529, EN 60730-1, EN 60947-1, EN 61010-1, EN IEC 61204, EN IEC 61293.

ANNEX IV EU DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY		Documentation	EN 60204-1, EN 60034-1, EN 60215, EN 60335-1, EN 60529, EN 60730-1, EN 60947-1, EN 61010-1, EN IEC 61204, EN IEC 61293.
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2.2.4. Radio Equipment Directive (RED) 2014/53/EU

The RED Radio Equipment Directive - 2014/53/EU is based on the NLF decision (EU) 768/2008. This means that it only contains essential requirements (in other words, general requirements) and the detailed technical requirements are transferred to standards harmonised with the directive. These standards provide state-of-the-art technical specifications allowing demonstration of compliance with the essential requirements of the directive, i.e.

1. Radio equipment shall be constructed so as to ensure:
 - (a) the protection of health and safety of persons and of domestic animals and the protection of property, including the objectives with respect to safety requirements set out in LVD Directive 2014/35/EU, but with no voltage limit applying;
 - (b) an adequate level of electromagnetic compatibility as set out in EMC Directive 2014/30/EU.
2. Radio equipment shall be so constructed that it both effectively uses and supports the efficient use of radio spectrum in order to avoid harmful interference.

For certain categories or classes of radio equipment, the Radio Equipment Directive additionally applies the provisions of Article 3.3 and, as of December 2024, the new Article 3.4. These additional essential requirements are:

- (a) interworking with accessories, in particular with common chargers;
- (b) interworking via networks with other radio equipment;
- (c) connection to interfaces of the appropriate type throughout the EU;
- (d) prevention of network damage / misuse of network resources (part of cybersecurity introduced by 2022/30 Delegated Act);
- (e) protection of personal data and privacy (part of cybersecurity introduced by 2022/30 Delegated Act);
- (f) protection against fraud (part of cybersecurity introduced by 2022/30 Delegated Act);
- (g) ensuring access to emergency services;
- (h) facilitating operation for people with disabilities;
- (i) ensuring that only software that has been demonstrated to be compliant in combination with the radio equipment can be loaded.

The requirements of the standards covering essential requirements could be attributes to evaluate within AgrifoodTEF.

The full list of currently harmonised standards here: <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/59954>. It is expected that new harmonised standards related to Cybersecurity i.e., "Network protection", "Personal data and privacy" and "Anti-fraud measures" will appear on the list latest by August 2025. These standards result from new essential requirements that have been recently introduced to the Radio Equipment Directive (RED 2014/53/EU) by Delegated Act 2022/30. These new harmonised standards will also apply to agrifood equipment connected to the Internet using radio modules (e.g. GSM, LTE, Wifi, Bluetooth, etc).

Table 5. LVD Low Voltage Directive - 2014/35/EU attributes and related standards

RED Radio Equipment Directive - 2014/53/EU			
Article (only relevant one to AgrifoodTEF)	Attributes to evaluate	(Present/future) Potential standards for conformity assessment	
THE MAIN BODY OF THE ACT	Article 3 Essential requirements	Conformity Radio spectrum Cybersecurity aspects related to internet connection Robotic machines	ETSI 300 328 / ETSI 301 893 / ETSI 300 220
	Article 4 Provision of information on the compliance of combinations of radio equipment and software	Conformity Radio spectrum Cybersecurity aspects related to internet connection Robotic machines	ETSI 300 328 / ETSI 301 893 / ETSI 300 220
	Article 10 Obligations of manufacturers	Documentation	/
	Article 11 Authorised representatives	Documentation	/
	Article 12 Obligations of importers	Documentation	/
	Article 13 Obligations of distributors	Documentation	/

	<p>Article 16 Presumption of conformity of radio equipment</p>	<p>Conformity Radio spectrum Robotic machines</p>	<p>ETSI 300 328 / ETSI 301 893 / ETSI 300 220</p>
	<p>Article 17 Conformity assessment procedures</p>	<p>Conformity Radio spectrum Cybersecurity aspects related to internet connection Robotic machines</p>	<p>ETSI 300 328 / ETSI 301 893 / ETSI 300 220</p>
	<p>Article 18 EU declaration of conformity</p>	<p>Documentation</p>	<p>ETSI 300 328 / ETSI 301 893 / ETSI 300 220</p>
	<p>Article 19 General principles of the CE marking</p>	<p>Documentation</p>	<p>/</p>
	<p>Article 20 Rules and conditions for affixing the CE marking and the identification number of the notified body</p>	<p>Documentation</p>	<p>/</p>

	Article 21 Technical documentation	Conformity Radio spectrum Cybersecurity aspects related to internet connection	ETSI 300 328 / ETSI 301 893 / ETSI 300 220
ANNEX V CONTENTS OF TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION		Documentation	ETSI 300 328 / ETSI 301 893 / ETSI 300 220
ANNEX VI EU DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY		Documentation	ETSI 300 328 / ETSI 301 893 / ETSI 300 220
ANNEX VII SIMPLIFIED EU DECLARATION OF CONFORMITY		Documentation	/

2.3. Cybersecurity Act 2019/881

The Cybersecurity Act (Regulation (EU) 2019/881) establishes a comprehensive legal framework for cybersecurity within the European Union. It strengthens the role of ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) by granting it a permanent mandate and a broader scope of responsibilities, particularly in supporting member states and private entities in improving their cybersecurity practices. The Act also introduces the European Cybersecurity Certification

Framework, a system designed to harmonize and standardize the certification of ICT products, services, and processes across the EU. By providing clear criteria and levels of assurance, the framework aims to enhance trust and security in the digital market while reducing fragmentation between member states.

One of the key certification schemes under the Cybersecurity Act is the European Union Common Criteria (EUCC). The EUCC adapts the internationally recognized Common Criteria (ISO/IEC 15408) to the European context. It offers a unified approach to assessing and certifying the security of ICT products by defining protection profiles and security targets. This ensures that products meet specified security requirements, allowing certifications to be mutually recognized across EU member states. The close link between the Cybersecurity Act and the EUCC lies in their shared objective to create a coherent and trustworthy cybersecurity ecosystem, facilitating secure market access while supporting manufacturers and developers in demonstrating the robustness of their products.

Table 6. Cybersecurity Act 2019/881 & European common criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme (EUCC) 2024/483 attributes and related standards

Cybersecurity Act 2019/881 & European common criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme (EUCC) 2024/483			
Article		Attributes to evaluate	(Present/future) Potential standards for conformity assessment
CYBERSECURITY ACT 2019/881	Article 46 European cybersecurity certification framework	Availability, integrity, authenticity, confidentiality	/
	Article 51 Security objectives of European cybersecurity certification schemes	Availability Accessibility Life-cycle Secure access Risk analysis Logging Availability after accident Cybersecure by design Vulnerabilities testing	ISO/WD 24882 CEN ISO/TR 22100
	Article 52 Assurance levels of European cybersecurity certification schemes	Assess assurance level Technical documentation "Elementary assurance level" product cybersecurity compliance "Substantial assurance level" product cybersecurity compliance "High assurance level" product cybersecurity compliance Technical tests	CB Scheme on CYBR ISO/IEC/TS 23532-1

	Article 55 Supplementary cybersecurity information for certified ICT products, ICT services and ICT processes	Transparency with end-users	CEN ISO/TR 22100 EN ISO/IEC 27001
EUROPEAN COMMON CRITERIA-BASED CYBERSECURITY CERTIFICATION SCHEME (EUCC) 2024/483	(2)	Privacy protection Methodology for IT security Evaluation	ISO 18045 ISO/IEC 15408
	(3)	Risk analysis	/
	(5)	Assurance level analysis Risk level analysis	ISO/IEC 15408
	(26)	Change impact analysis Desk assessment Vulnerability disclosure	EN ISO/CEI 29147 ISO/IEC 15408
	Article 33 Vulnerability management procedures	Vulnerability handling processes	EN ISO/IEC 30111
	Article 34 Vulnerability impact analysis	Impact analysis of vulnerabilities Potential attack and vulnerability handling	ISO/WD 24882
	Annex IV.3 Assurance continuity and certificate review	Change impact analysis	/

2.4. Data Act 2023/2854

The Data Act, a proposed regulation by the European Commission, aims to establish a framework for fair access to and use of data within the European Union. It seeks to empower individuals and businesses by clarifying data usage rights and ensuring that data generated by devices and services can be accessed and shared under fair and transparent conditions. The Act promotes data portability and interoperability, enabling innovation and competition while safeguarding the interests of data holders and users. This framework aims to create clear rules for data sharing, enhancing trust and supporting technological development across sectors.

Table 7. Data Act 2023/2854 attributes and related standards

Data Act 2023/2854			
Article	Requirement	(Present/future) Potential standards for conformity assessment	
DATA ACT 2023/2854	Chapter II Business to consumer and business to business data sharing	B2C and B2B data sharing upon users' request Transparency with end-users Data sharing Ensure Fair and Non-Discriminatory Data Sharing Accessibility Access by design Access by request Sharing by request Data interoperability	ISO/IEC 27001 ISO/IEC 27017 ISO/IEC 27018 W3C Data on the Web Best Practices GDPR Certification BSI PAS 440 ISO/TS 8000 GO-FAIR Principles ISO 22301
	Chapter III Obligations for data holders obliged to make data available pursuant to Union law	FRAND conditions Compensation Dispute settlement	ISO/IEC 38505 ISO/IEC 27701 BSI PAS 440 ISO 22301
	Chapter IV Unfair contractual terms related to data access and use between enterprises	Unilaterally imposed unfair contractual terms	ISO/IEC 38505 ISO/IEC 27701
	Chapter VI Switching between data processing services	Removing obstacles to effective switching Switching cloud services Technical obligations Contractual terms Contractual transparency Obligation of good faith	ISO/IEC 27017 ISO/IEC 27018 ISO/IEC 27701 BSI PAS 440 EU Cloud Code of Conduct (CoC) Certification
	Chapter VIII Interoperability	Essential requirements regarding interoperability of data, of data sharing mechanisms and services, as well as of common European data spaces In-parallel use of data processing Services	ISO/IEC 27001 ISO/IEC 19941 IEEE P2302 W3C Data on the Web Best Practices ISO 22301

2.5. Recent perspectives on a harmonised legal basis for European food safety control

Regulation 882/2004 emphasizes that the frequency of official controls should be both regular and proportionate to the associated risks. This approach considers the outcomes of checks conducted by feed and food business operators

through HACCP-based control systems or Quality Assurance Programs that align with feed and food law requirements. Currently, ISO is developing a dedicated standard for food safety management systems, known as ISO 22000.

This international standard outlines the requirements for organizations within the food chain to demonstrate their ability to manage food safety hazards effectively, ensuring the consistent production of safe final products. It aims to meet agreed customer and regulatory food safety standards while improving customer satisfaction through the efficient control of food safety hazards and regular system updates. ISO 22000 enables organizations to:

- Plan, design, implement, maintain, and update a food safety management system that ensures the safety of food products when consumed as intended ;
- Evaluate and meet customer requirements related to food safety, demonstrating compliance with mutually agreed expectations ;
- Communicate effectively with customers and stakeholders throughout the food chain ;
- Adhere to applicable regulatory food safety requirements ;
- Ensure compliance with their declared food safety policy ;
- Demonstrate their compliance to relevant parties ;
- Pursue certification or registration of their food safety management system through an external body.

The standard is designed to be versatile and applicable to organizations of all types and sizes, irrespective of their role in the food chain. This includes entities directly involved in any step of the food production process, such as feed producers, farmers, food manufacturers, retailers, caterers, and service providers in cleaning, transportation, and storage. It also extends to organizations indirectly linked to the food chain, such as suppliers of equipment, packaging, and food contact materials.

ISO 22000 is structured similarly to ISO 9001, which focuses on quality management, and integrates food safety management with HACCP principles established by the Codex Alimentarius Commission. This approach ensures a comprehensive and effective framework for maintaining food safety across the supply chain.

2.6. Conclusion

This section has provided a detailed overview of key regulations and their associated standards, whether harmonized or not, organized around thematic requirements. By doing so, it aims to equip project partners with a clear understanding of the existing regulatory landscape and the tools available to navigate it. The regulatory framework remains dynamic, with ongoing developments such as the AI Act and the Data Act. While these regulations do not yet offer stable references, this deliverable proposes valuable guidance and pointers, through associated standards and frameworks, to support the development of services aligned with these evolving requirements. It is important to note that both the regulations and the associated standards were not necessarily designed with AI-based systems in mind, which may require adaptations and further analysis to address the specific challenges posed by such technologies. This approach helps the partners stay up-to-date with regulatory changes and meet compliance requirements in their specific areas of expertise.

3. TEF involvement in conformity assessment services

This chapter translates the positioning of TEF partners that may propose and implement conformity assessment services to the previously presented European regulations. The first section relates of the results of a workshop and a survey sent to AgrifoodTEF partners about their capabilities to implement services related to the attributes / standards extracted in Chapter 2. The second contribution of this chapter consists of lessons learned and feedback of an example of WP3 service delivered by RISE.

3.1. Survey of TEF partners

We conducted a survey between TEF partners to probe fields of application and requirements from main European regulations: the AI Act, the Machinery Regulation, the Cybersecurity Act and common criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme (European Union Common Criteria, EUCC), and the Data Act. The objective of this survey is to highlight the key interests of conformity assessment providers in AgrifoodTEF in implementing new services in the following years, and to better understand gaps to be filled, guided by future standards (e.g. lack of testing procedures).

This survey was conducted among the main TEF partners involved in WP3 and/or proposing WP3 services in AgrifoodTEF’s catalogue: LNE, ILVO, INRAE, DTI, FHWN, Josephinum Research, INRIA, HISPATEC, RGRD, and University de Lleida. The following results depicts TEF partners aspirations in terms of EU regulations attributes to cover in new conformity assessment services.

3.1.1. AI Act 2024/1689

The first questions asked were about the AI Act keywords (previously indicated attributes) relevancy and importance for TEF partners and standards considered relevant that answers some of the attributes of the AI Act. The following graphs illustrate the results of this poll.

Figure 8. Results of TEF partners survey concerning the AI Act

Abbreviation	Standard name
ISO 42001	AI Quality Management System
EN ISO/IEC 23894	Guidance on risk management
ISO/IEC/TR 24029	Assessment of the robustness of neural networks
EN ISO/IEC 25059	Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) - Quality model for AI systems
prEN ISO/IEC 5259	Data quality for analytics and machine learning
CEN/CLC/TR 17894	Artificial Intelligence Conformity Assessment

The results shows that TEF partners are involved in delivering conformity assessment to standard services mainly regarding technical safety requirements such as availability and integrity of systems, safety tests and also to data and data governance issues. Some topics such as technical documentation to provide transparency or for the risk management of an AI product are difficult to cover due to lack of standards (see Section 2.1) and legal expertise among TEF partners to provide relevant TEF service.

3.1.2. Machine Regulation 2023/1230

Regarding the Machine Regulation, many technical standards propose safety requirements that could be tested and that are already included in TEF catalogue of services. The survey questions aimed to understand better the actual positioning of TEF partners regarding related services and their feedback with past TEF clients. The following graphs shows a summary of the results.

Figure 9. Results of TEF partners survey concerning the Machine Regulation

The results depicts a very equal contributions of TEF partners to provide technical safety tests among the main criteria of the Machinery Regulation, except for the safety related to the Operational Design Domain. The overall feedback of TEF partners is that it is difficult and costly to set-up a test protocol for this last criteria. Indeed, testing all the edge-cases or all the combinations of abnormal situations that can occur to an AI or robotic system in an agrifood environment could be endless due to the complexity of open environments of farms. It may be considered by some TEF partners for software only AI products or indoor robotic systems.

Secondly, TEF partners are more willing to provide technical safety tests related to AI (same conclusion as in Section 3.1.1) such as perception or navigation functions that have explicit requirements in some standards (e.g. performance level in ISO 18497), rather than mechanical components of a robot (like end-effectors and two-hand control devices) or risk management related topics (evaluation and risk mitigation). In future works, AgrifoodTEF will investigate deeper these attributes to provide TEF clients with more practical services that answers the need of assessing the risk management protocols and technical documentation related to an AI product.

3.1.3. Cybersecurity Act 2019/881 and European common criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme (EUCC) 2024/482

The last series of questions concerns the cybersecurity of AI and robotics products in the agrifood sector. Currently, AgrifoodTEF only provides basic cybersecurity services such as assessing risk analysis, making pentests of testing clearly identified vulnerabilities. TEF partners were asked about their capability and will to deliver cybersecurity services, their key interests (correlated with attributes presented in Section 2.3) in cybersecurity. Finally, we asked TEF partners about relevant cybersecurity-related standards with respect to their activities and skills. This polls' objective is to identify some relevant standards to study further that could provide guidelines to implement new WP 3 services.

COULD YOUR ORGANIZATION DELIVER CYBERSECURITY SERVICES ?

CYBERSECURITY RELEVANT ATTRIBUTES FOR TEF PARTNERS

Abbreviation	Standard name
ISO/IEC 15408	Framework for evaluating the security properties of IT products and systems
ISO 18045	Evaluation criteria for IT security – Methodology for IT security evaluation
EN ISO/CEI 29147	Information technology – Security techniques – Vulnerability disclosure
EN ISO/IEC 30111	Information technology – Security techniques – Vulnerability handling processes
ISO/IEC/TS 23532	Requirements for the competence of IT security testing and evaluation laboratories
EN ISO/IEC 27001	Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection – Information security management systems

Figure 10. Results of TEF partners survey concerning the Cybersecurity Act 2019/881 & European common criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme (EUCC) 2024/483

Firstly, half of the partners who participated in the survey are not able to implement cybersecurity services for diverse reasons (lack of skill, not relevant regarding their core activity, could not find market needs ...). Less than half partners could cover all the areas of application of the European common criteria-based cybersecurity certification scheme (EUCC) 2024/482 equally. In detail, many criteria related to technical tests are covered but not those related to product or company documentation such as logging and journalizing developments and updates of systems. Section 2.3 confirms that risk analysis and change impact analysis are lacking some standards.

The last graphs shows that cybersecurity properties such as vulnerability disclosure are relevant and could be covered by TEF partners (ISO/IEC 15408 and EN ISO/CEI 29147). These standards will be studied further and could potentially provide AI and robotics companies a better understanding of cybersecurity compliance.

3.2. Case study of delivering a service related to conformity assessment

This section gives a feedback and lessons learned when delivering WP3 services related to helping SMEs understand their AI and robotics product applicable regulations and build a conformity assessment roadmap. Those recommendations are based on RISE experience while delivering these two WP3 services to multiple TEF clients:

- S00007 – Evaluation of conformity roadmap for an innovation
- S00009 – Compliance assessment for robotic machines.

The lessons learned and best practices are based on approximately 10 services delivered between 2023 and 2024 and has been exposed in November 2024, describing the recent issues faced in services.

3.2.1. Best practices during contracting phase

- **Expect prospecting/management time:** the onboarding phase of a company is extremely important and time consuming. It is indeed mandatory to explain completely the output delivered to a customer as it could vary from an initial study and a few recommendations to a complete conformity assessment plan. It is also important to describe the relevant service and other services that might better fit the TEF client's needs.
- **Evaluate TEF client TRL:** companies are often too low TRL for conformity assessment services. They usually are interested in anticipating regulations and future standards upstream of their AI product development.
- **Agreement on expectations/output:** it is important to keep some flexibility while offering these kind of services that may require more workforce depending on the deepness of the study to be carried out, the costs and timeframes of the service. This needs to be understood by both parties before signing the contract and the TEF partner has the responsibility of judging that he has completed the service delivery or if it needs more hours of work. Then, both parties can decide to make amendments when it is needed.
- **Shared responsibilities:** the TEF client has to be aware of his responsibility of sharing technical information, documents, AI models, datasets, and any other technical aspects that may help the TEF partner to understand and provide a complete analysis.
- **TEF partner is also learning:** in a constantly evolving regulation and standardization, it should be made clear with the TEF client that each partner has limited means and knowledge and can only use available resources.

3.2.2. Best practices during service delivery

- **Expect the unexpected:** External factors such as bad weather or unforeseen circumstances can disrupt service delivery. It is essential to maintain flexibility and prepare contingency plans to handle such situations effectively.
- **Promotion is always appreciated:** While promoting the service is valuable, it is critical to remain independent and avoid making valuations of the company to ensure objectivity and impartiality.
- **Testing reveals more than expected:** Although the focus may be on testing AI systems, often other aspects, such as the system's strength or reliability, come under scrutiny. These unexpected insights should be documented and communicated appropriately.
- **Software updates and service scope:** If the company makes a software update during the service period, it may result in a new or extended service scope. Clear communication is necessary to address this and agree on any required adjustments.
- **Agility and iterations:** Changes to the initial agreement may be necessary. Adopting an iterative and agile approach allows for modifications when justified. Both parties should ensure these changes are well-documented and mutually agreed upon.

- **Information flow:** Ensure all agreed-upon information, such as log data or other technical details, is received in a timely manner. Incomplete or delayed information can impact the quality of the analysis and conclusions.
- **Tracking agreed hours:** It is important to monitor the hours spent on the service in line with the initial agreement. This helps manage expectations and facilitates discussions about any additional time required to complete the service.

3.2.3. Best practices after the service delivery

- **Addressing unexpected test outcomes:** When test results deviate from expectations, the causes and implications should be clearly identified and communicated. Documenting these findings ensures transparency and supports the formulation of further actions.
- **Planning subsequent steps:** The outcomes of the service should be reviewed to determine whether additional services, such as further testing or analysis, are necessary. This assessment facilitates a structured follow-up process.
- **Incorporating lessons learned:** Evaluating the service delivery process enables the identification of strengths and areas for improvement. Documenting these insights contributes to refining practices and enhancing the effectiveness of future services.

3.2.4. Future actions and recommendations

How are we sharing knowledge among us?

Current mechanisms for sharing knowledge within the TEF ecosystem include:

- **WP3 monthly meetings:** These are valuable for tactical updates but could be improved with dedicated time slots for peer-to-peer sharing of lessons learned.
- **F2F meetings:** These allow deeper discussion, retrospectives, and scenario-based learning. Consider making service retrospectives a standing agenda item.
- **Service delivery follow-up logs:** Encourage each TEF partner to document key challenges and insights after service completion in a shared repository

How to apply these best practices

To effectively apply these best practices in TEF service delivery, a **structured operational framework** should be adopted across all TEF partners. Recommended approaches include but are not limited to:

- **Standardized onboarding checklists:** Create templates that ensure consistent explanation of outputs, assessment of TRL, shared responsibilities, and flexibility clauses.
- **Training modules for TEF partners:** Build internal training to raise awareness of the typical challenges and teach how to implement agile service delivery models, especially for newer partners.
- **Service delivery protocols:** Define clear, repeatable steps for managing service adjustments, unexpected outcomes, and iteration handling.
- **Client-facing materials:** Develop educational materials to align clients' expectations, their role in the service, and the evolving nature of AI conformity assessments.
- **Documentation systems:** Use shared tools (e.g. SharePoint) to store non-confidential test results, learnings, client communications, and decisions on changes to scope or deliverables.

Challenges in changing how TEF partners deliver services

Changing established practices often meets resistance. Anticipated challenges include:

- **Variation in partner maturity:** Some partners may lack the internal processes or resources to implement agile or client-centered approaches.

- **Inconsistent interpretation of flexibility:** What one partner considers a minor scope change, another may see as a contract breach, creating trust or billing issues.
- **Time/resource pressure:** Best practices like thorough onboarding or iterative testing require more time, which might conflict with KPIs or funding expectations.
- **Learning curve:** Adapting to fast-changing AI regulations and integrating them into services in real-time is demanding, especially for smaller teams.
- **Client pushback:** Clients may resist contributing significant technical documentation or be unwilling to accept the iterative/agile delivery model.

The following sections provide suggestions to improve the services delivery. These suggestions may be partially or fully implemented by TEF partners, but should preserve a certain level of autonomy and allow for adaptation to specific circumstances.

Contracting phase

1. **Establish a structured onboarding process to define relevant services**
 - Create standardized onboarding documentation to clearly define deliverables (e.g., initial study vs. full conformity assessment).
 - Provide a comparison chart of available services to help clients choose what best fit their needs.
2. **Define scope and flexibility in contracts**
 - Clarify ownership of decisions regarding service completion and when additional hours/work are needed.
 - Create templates for contingency plans addressing common external disruptions (e.g., weather, environmental, technical).
3. **Clarify technical scope**
 - Implement a mandatory TRL evaluation form or checklist during prospection to identify if a client is suitable for conformity assessment services.
 - Offer alternative inside AgrifoodTEF advisory or preparatory services for clients with lower TRLs.
 - Include a “flexibility clause” in all contracts to allow for scope expansion with pre-agreed processes for amendments.
 - Freeze the hardware/software testing version of a client technology and formalize a process to reassess and revalidate scope when clients introduce updates mid-service.
4. **Reinforce client responsibilities**
 - Add a client responsibility statement to contracts, listing required deliverables (technical documents etc.). Deliver documentation in time.
 - Develop a pre-contract checklist to ensure clients understand and accept these responsibilities.
5. **Set expectations about evolving knowledge**
 - Add disclaimers or transparency notes in contracts to clarify that partners operate within evolving regulatory frameworks and limited resources.
6. **Track hours transparently**
 - If compatible with the TEF partner internal policy, implement and use timesheets or hour-tracking dashboards shared with the client to keep both sides aligned on work effort and limits.

Service delivery phase

7. **Maintain objectivity in promotion**
 - Develop communication guidelines for TEF partners that encourage neutral promotion of services without valuing or endorsing clients.
 - Involve the client in a broader TEF promotion effort through testimonials and success stories about their journey within AgrifoodTEF.
8. **Leverage testing Insights**

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- Introduce a “surprise findings” section in test reports to document additional insights discovered during testing.

9. Implement root cause analysis for unexpected results

- Use structured tools (e.g., “5 Whys” or Fishbone Diagrams) to analyse and explain unexpected test outcomes in client reports
- General improvement on service delivery: delays and deadlines meeting, disclosing of issues, delivery quality and so on.

10. Ensure timely data transfer

- Facilitate the data transfer step using an easy to use online tool for traceable information sharing.

Post-delivery phase

11. Offer follow-up planning templates

- Include a “next steps” section in final reports, with tailored recommendations for additional services within AgrifoodTEF, while carefully avoiding technical recommendations directed at the company.

12. Systematize lessons learned

- Conduct internal debriefs after each service to document lessons in a central knowledge base.
- Conduct surveys and ask customers about their opinions about the services offered.
- Regularly review and update templates based on these insights.

4. Gap analysis and strategic needs

This chapter presents a comprehensive analysis of the current capabilities of TEF partners in relation to regulatory compliance and market demands, identifying critical gaps and strategic needs to enhance the consortium’s service portfolio. By synthesizing the present state of technical expertise available among TEF partners, alongside detailed mapping of client requirements, a clear understanding of areas requiring reinforcement to meet evolving regulatory frameworks, including the AI Act, Machinery Regulation, Data Act, EMC, LVD, and RED directives, is established.

The analysis further highlights priority gaps impacting TEF’s capacity to deliver full conformity assessment services, with a special focus on cybersecurity challenges and emerging compliance mandates. Based on these findings, this chapter outlines strategic actions aimed at addressing these gaps through targeted partnerships, skill development, and innovation in conformity assessment services, and alignment with state-of-the-art standards.

Ultimately, the gap analysis informs the roadmap for future service evolution, ensuring TEF remains responsive to client needs and regulatory developments, while maintaining a leading role in advancing trustworthy AI and robotics technologies across Europe.

4.1. Synthesis of current capabilities

The analysis of current capabilities across AgrifoodTEF partners reveals a solid foundation in technical performance testing, particularly in perception, navigation, and environmental interaction of robotic systems. These competencies are well aligned with safety requirements from the Machinery Regulation and support key aspects of real-world validation under the AI Act. However, the survey also highlights significant gaps in non-functional assessment domains that are equally critical for regulatory compliance. Fewer partners reported operational readiness to perform evaluations related to lifecycle risk management, incident logging, traceability, or the production and audit of technical documentation, all of which are essential for high-risk AI systems under Articles 10 to 18 of the AI Act. The lack of standardized processes, limited legal and regulatory expertise, and the absence of shared documentation templates currently limit the ability to offer comprehensive conformity assessment services across the network. These findings underscore the need for targeted capacity building, including training on regulatory frameworks, development of shared tools, and strategic partnerships to ensure AgrifoodTEF can address the full spectrum of AI compliance requirements in the agrifood domain.

4.2. Identified regulatory gaps

The following sections present a detailed mapping of TEF partners' capabilities against key regulatory requirements identified in Chapter 2. Each table focuses on a specific regulation, highlighting the articles to be assessed and for which we have identified some current missing capability, the description of the missing capability and the gap identified, and the impact on a future service readiness and its development priority with respect to the current standardization projects. This structured overview supports the identification of priority areas for development and informs the strategic roadmap for expanding AgrifoodTEF’s conformity assessment services.

AI Act

Regulatory Area	Capability Missing in TEF partners	Gap identified	Impact on service readiness	Priority
Art. 10 – Data & Governance	Security, pseudonymization	Partial security, no ISO/IEC 27001 or GDPR certification. No audited framework for data processing	Legal vulnerabilities in case of personal data processing	Medium
Art. 11 – Technical Documentation	Documentation compliance, recorded events	Incomplete knowledge of formal requirements under the AI Act + no standardized template	Blocks access to CE marking for high-risk AI systems	Very high
Art. 12 – Logging	Continuous logging, results verification	No certifiable or auditable logging systems. No formal logging/supervision mechanisms	Impossible to ensure traceability required by the AI Act	Very high
Art. 13 – Transparency & Information	Interpretability, outputs, explanations, user instructions	Technical skills exist, but documentation is not standardized. Lack of harmonized guides or formats	Fails to meet the transparency needed for regulatory acceptance	High
Art. 15 – Robustness, Cybersecurity	Resistance to attacks (poisoning, adversarial)	Low integration of attack testing in evaluations. Lack of advanced cybersecurity expertise (e.g., ISO/IEC 24029)	Fails to meet expected safety levels	High
Art. 17 – Quality Management System	Quality monitoring, verification, maintenance, resource management	Very few partners use ISO 42001 or equivalent + poor understanding of the requirements	Prevents full approval of the system	Medium
Art. 18 – Documentation Retention	Approved modifications, document retention	No formal versioning or standardized archiving processes. No standardized pipeline for compliant documentation	Cannot be demonstrated in a post-market audit	High

Overall, the AgrifoodTEF consortium offers only limited coverage of the AI Act. While a few services exist related to documentation review and quality management system assessment, very few address the technical aspects of performance evaluation, such as robustness and cybersecurity, or requirements related to transparency and logging. Many of the relevant standards in these areas are still under development, and dedicated training within the project will be necessary to ensure proper understanding and implementation.

Machine Regulation

Regulatory Area	Capability Missing in TEF partners	Gap identified	Impact on service readiness	Priority
Art. (28), (32),	Consideration of software	No test benches or	Potential non-compliance	Very

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(36) – Product Lifecycle	evolution and increasing autonomy	procedures for update revalidation	in case of automatic updates / edge-AI	high
Annex III.1.1.9	Protection against (cyber) corruption	Lack of control flow integrity testing, no advanced pentesting. Low maturity in embedded cybersecurity	Non-compliance with machinery cybersecurity requirements	High
Annex III.1.2.2	Control devices	No automated ODD/edge-case test benches	Inability to guarantee safety of autonomous starts	High
Annex III.3.2.4	Remote supervision function	Limited equipment and expertise for testing remote H-M interaction. Lack of UX analysis protocols/standards for agricultural control stations	Low regulatory credibility for remote use	Medium
Annex IV – Technical Documentation	Transparency, product limitations, tests performed	No harmonized standards for templates or shared models	Inconsistency in compliance services provided	High

Regarding the Machine Regulation 2023/1230, several critical gaps persist among AgrifoodTEF partners, especially in areas related to the software-driven lifecycle of autonomous systems. There is currently no testing infrastructure to support update revalidation, posing a serious risk of non-compliance in the case of self-learning or evolving AI functionalities. Additionally, the absence of automated test benches for operational design domain (ODD) edge-case scenarios limits the capacity to ensure safe activation of autonomous control devices. Remote supervision remains another weak point, as few partners are equipped to assess human-machine interfaces or apply UX standards specific to agricultural contexts. Lastly, the lack of harmonized documentation templates and structured reporting models contributes to inconsistencies in conformity assessment services. Addressing these gaps is essential to deliver robust and credible services aligned with the updated regulatory expectations for modern machinery.

Data Act

Regulatory Area	Capability Missing in TEF partners	Gap identified	Impact on service readiness	Priority
Chap. II – B2B / B2C	Direct B2B data re-use conditions	No auditing service or user-side transparency assessment due to lack of a harmonized standard	Conflicts with the spirit of the Data Act: data lock-in / mistrust	High
Chap. II	Data accessibility by design (access by design)	No team expertise to conduct this assessment	Prevents compliance from the design stage (incompatibility with Art. 3)	High
Chap. II	Interoperability of formats and interfaces	No team expertise to conduct this assessment	Low data reusability, barrier to agricultural data sharing	Very high
Chap. VI	Portability between cloud services, reversibility	No audit of data reversibility (vendor lock-in). No effective migration or portability testing	TEF clients locked into non-compliant providers	Very high
Chap. VIII	Interoperability of services	No interoperability	Potential incompatibility	High

	and data spaces	framework (e.g., aligned with W3C, GO-FAIR, ISO 19941)	with future European data spaces	
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With respect to the Data Act, AgrifoodTEF partners currently face significant limitations in their ability to support data governance and interoperability requirements. There is no established service to assess B2B or B2C data reuse conditions or to audit transparency from the user’s perspective, leaving a gap in compliance with fair data-sharing obligations. Additionally, no partner has the technical expertise to evaluate “accessibility by design,” a core concept of the regulation that is essential from the earliest stages of product development. The lack of competencies in data format and interface interoperability presents a major obstacle to agricultural data sharing and reuse. Moreover, there is no capability to assess data portability or reversibility between cloud providers, exposing TEF clients to vendor lock-in risks and non-compliance with Chapter VI requirements. Finally, AgrifoodTEF does not yet provide a framework aligned with emerging standards for interoperability across European data spaces, which may hinder future integration efforts. Bridging these gaps will require dedicated expertise, strong collaboration with the AgriDataSpace initiative, and alignment with international best practices such as W3C and GO-FAIR.

ElectroMagnetic Compatibility

Regulatory Area	Capability Missing in TEF partners	Gap identified	Impact on service readiness	Priority
Art. 6 / Art. 13 / Annex I	Electromagnetic compliance (emissions & immunity)	Few TEF partners are equipped to test EMC emissions or disturbances in agricultural environments. No shared or portable EMC infrastructure suited for robotic systems	Inability to demonstrate compliance with essential EMC requirements → CE marking blocked	Very high
Art. 7 to 10	Technical documentation by manufacturers/importers/distributors	Poor understanding of mandatory elements in EMC technical documentation	Gaps in regulatory traceability for market surveillance authorities	Medium
Art. 15 / Annex IV	EU Declaration of Conformity (DoC) for EMC	Non-standard or incomplete declaration templates observed. Lack of checklists or cross-validation mechanisms	Legal risks in case of audit or post-market inspection	Medium

In the domain of electromagnetic compatibility (EMC), AgrifoodTEF partners currently face significant limitations that directly impact their ability to support CE marking for AI and robotic systems. Only a few partners are equipped to perform EMC testing related to emissions and immunity, particularly in open and variable agricultural environments. There is no shared or mobile EMC testing infrastructure within the network tailored to the needs of robotic or AI-driven equipment, which severely hinders the ability to demonstrate compliance with essential requirements under Articles 6 and 13 and Annex I. Additionally, understanding of the regulatory expectations regarding EMC technical documentation remains limited, leading to gaps in traceability and potentially weak responses to market surveillance audits. Furthermore, EU Declarations of Conformity (DoC) are often incomplete or lack standardization, as cross-validation tools or templates are not consistently applied across partners. These gaps introduce legal risks and could prevent clients from successfully placing their products on the European market. Addressing these challenges will require investment in testing infrastructure, shared documentation tools, and training on EMC regulatory compliance.

Low Voltage Directive

Regulatory Area	Capability Missing in TEF partners	Gap identified	Impact on service readiness	Priority
Art. 3 / Annex I – Essential Requirements	Electrical safety (protection against shocks, overheating, arcing, etc.)	No dedicated low-voltage electrical testing infrastructure	Inability to demonstrate LVD regulatory compliance → CE marking not possible	Very high
Art. 3	Tolerance to voltage fluctuations	No procedure to validate performance under extreme or unstable voltage	Risk of product failure in agricultural conditions (generators, batteries)	High
Annex I – 1(b)	Requirements on temperature, radiation, etc.	No testing for heating, arcing, or thermal dissipation performed in TEF test scenarios. Lack of benches or sensors for embedded thermal analysis	Inability to demonstrate intrinsic safety during charging / intensive use	Medium to High
Annex III	EU Declaration of Conformity	Partial or non-compliant DoC templates observed. No cross-validation process based on harmonized LVD standards	Legal risk if product is placed on the market with invalid declaration	Medium

AgriFoodTEF currently lacks the infrastructure and procedures needed to support compliance with the Low Voltage Directive. Critical gaps include the absence of low-voltage electrical testing, no validation of voltage fluctuation tolerance, and missing thermal safety assessments. Additionally, Declaration of Conformity templates are inconsistent and lack standardization, creating legal risks. These issues must be addressed to enable CE marking and ensure safe deployment of electrical equipment in agrifood environments.

Radio Equipment Directive

Regulatory Area	Capability Missing in TEF partners	Gap identified	Impact on service readiness	Priority
Art. 3(1)(a)	Health & safety (EMF exposure, electrical safety)	No tools to assess SAR or compliance with EN 50665 / EN 62311	Risk to users or environment → CE marking blocked	Very high
Art. 3(1)(b)	Electromagnetic compatibility (EMC)	EMC tests rarely performed for radio equipment (with integrated antennas). Lack of cross-validation with EMC Directive requirements	Implicit non-compliance → product not tested as a system	High
Art. 3(2)	Efficient use of radio spectrum	Lack of RF measurement capabilities (spectrum / intermodulation analysis) except for 1 partner for WiFi, Bluetooth and short range devices technologies	Risk of regulated interference, non-compliance with authorized frequency bands	Very high

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Art. 3(3)(d)	Cybersecurity: Protection against network harm and service degradation	New essential requirement for equipment placed into the European market after August 1, 2025	Risk to users → CE marking blocked	Very high
Art. 3(3)(e)	Cybersecurity: Safeguards for personal data and user privacy	New essential requirement for equipment placed into the European market after August 1, 2025	Risk to users → CE marking blocked	Very high
Art. 3(3)(f)	Cybersecurity: Measures to prevent fraud in radio equipment handling virtual currency	New essential requirement for equipment placed into the European market after August 1, 2025	Risk to users → CE marking blocked	Very high

AgrifoodTEF currently lacks key capabilities to ensure compliance with the Radio Equipment Directive. There are no tools for assessing EMF exposure or radio frequency performance, and EMC testing for radio-enabled devices is limited and fragmented. Only a few partners can perform spectrum efficiency or intermodulation analysis, critical for avoiding interference. Moreover, with the new cybersecurity requirements under Articles 3(3)(d), (e), and (f) becoming mandatory in August 2025, the absence of cybersecurity evaluation services (e.g., for network protection, privacy, or anti-fraud) poses a major barrier to CE marking. Urgent investment and skill development are needed to address these high-priority gaps.

4.3. Conclusion on AgrifoodTEF capabilities analysis

The cross-analysis of regulatory requirements and current TEF partner capabilities reveals several critical gaps, particularly in areas such as technical documentation, lifecycle risk management, traceability, advanced cybersecurity, and data interoperability. These limitations are partly due to the still-limited number of harmonized standards applicable to AI systems in agrifood innovations and the rapidly evolving nature of new European regulations such as the AI Act, the Data Act, and the upcoming cybersecurity requirements under the updated RED Directive (Articles 3(3)(d), (e), and (f), applicable from August 2025). To address these challenges and ensure AgrifoodTEF remains at the forefront of regulatory support, a series of concrete measures must be implemented.

First, targeted partnerships will be essential to fill missing capabilities within the network, particularly for EMC/RED testing, documentation auditing, and cybersecurity certification (e.g., ISO/IEC 27001, EUCC). In parallel, the establishment of thematic working groups will help co-design new conformity assessment services based on market feedback and client needs. To accelerate internal capacity building, AgrifoodTEF will need to invest in training, recruitment, and external subcontracting in priority areas such as interoperability of data formats and interfaces, considerations on autonomous machines and standards for AI software traceability requirements.

These efforts should be closely linked to the ongoing development of shared testing protocols, which will be formalized in Deliverable D3.4, to ensure a coherent, harmonized, and state-of-the-art service offering across the consortium. A clear distinction should also be made between what TEF partners can develop internally and what must be sourced through collaboration or external providers.

Finally, client feedback and the market intelligence activities led under WP5 will serve as key inputs for prioritizing service development and informing future updates of the TEF service roadmap. This strategic alignment will enable AgrifoodTEF to adapt to real-world demand and maintain its leadership role in enabling conformity assessment for AI and robotics solutions in the agrifood sector.

4.4. Focus gap analysis in cybersecurity

Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2022/30, often referred to as the RED Delegated Act on cybersecurity, aims to strengthen the cybersecurity of internet-connected radio products available in the European Union (EU) by bringing into effect 3 additional essential requirements to the Radio Equipment Directive – RED (Directive 2014/53/EU).

Any devices that use radio technology for communication over the internet are in the scope of the RED Delegated Act and will need to be compliant with three new essential requirements when placed into the European market after August 1, 2025:

- Article 3(3)(d): Protection against network harm and service degradation
- Article 3(3)(e): Safeguards for personal data and user privacy
- Article 3(3)(f): Measures to prevent fraud in radio equipment handling virtual currency

It is therefore essential for AgrifoodTEF to strengthen its expertise and service offering in cybersecurity evaluation, in order to support manufacturers in meeting these new mandatory requirements and ensuring secure market access beyond 2025.

At the end of the Reporting Period 1, the service named “Vulnerability scan of agrifood-related AI or robotics software systems” service by Gradiant (Spanish node) is the only one that analyses and test cybersecurity measures. It is a specialized cybersecurity analysis tool designed to detect and report security flaws in software systems, it examines the codebase of a software system to identify potential vulnerabilities before the system is deployed in production. This ensures that the software is robust, secure, and compliant with cybersecurity best practices. Regular updates and vulnerability assessments are essential to mitigate risks and maintain the integrity of the deployed solutions. To effectively deliver and utilize this service, both service providers and users must possess specific technological competencies. Providers must have expertise in cloud-native technologies, including container orchestration, secure image handling, and automated vulnerability scanning tools. They must also be proficient in cybersecurity analysis, with the ability to interpret scan results, assess risk levels, and recommend mitigation strategies. On the user side, basic familiarity with container image creation, RESTful API integration, and secure software development practices is essential to ensure smooth collaboration and effective use of the service.

Currently, this vulnerability scanning service represents the sole cybersecurity-focused capability within the TEF consortium. Given the increasing complexity and prevalence of cybersecurity risks in AI and robotic systems, it is imperative that we expand our expertise and service offerings in this domain. The rapidly evolving threat landscape and tightening regulatory requirements demand a broader, more robust set of cybersecurity competencies to adequately support our clients. Without further development and diversification of cybersecurity services, the consortium risks falling short of market expectations and regulatory compliance needs.

The following table details missing technical capabilities among TEF partners for which we have identified the gap to fill, its impact on our service offering readiness and its priority level based on market intelligence studies done in WP5. This structured overview supports the identification of priority areas for development and informs the strategic roadmap for expanding AgrifoodTEF’s cybersecurity testing and assessment services.

Capability Missing	Gap identified	Impact on service readiness	Priority
Integration with EU-wide cybersecurity standards	Need to explicitly align with ENISA guidelines or NIS2 Directive	May limit adoption by public sector or regulated industries;	High

	requirements	potential non-compliance risks	
Multilingual support for reporting	Reports are only available in JSON/YAML or GUI in English	Limits accessibility for non-English-speaking stakeholders in multilingual EU member states	Medium
Data residency and sovereignty compliance	Need for better definition of data processing location or GDPR-compliant data handling practices	Could raise legal and trust concerns, especially for sensitive agrifood data	High
Sector-specific threat modeling for agriculture	Service does not provide tailored threat models or risk profiles for agrifood-specific systems (e.g., precision irrigation, livestock monitoring)	May overlook domain-specific vulnerabilities and attack vectors unique to agricultural systems	High

To address the current gaps in cybersecurity capabilities, TEF should prioritize upskilling its existing partners through targeted training such as the technical webinars dedicated to EDIHs and knowledge-sharing initiatives. This will strengthen core competencies in vulnerability assessment, penetration testing, and regulatory compliance. At the same time, complex certifications beyond the consortium’s current expertise should be outsourced to specialized third-party experts, ensuring quality and compliance without delaying service delivery.

Recruiting dedicated cybersecurity testing labs and subject matter experts is essential to rapidly expand TEF’s service portfolio and respond to growing market demands. A clear strategy must be established to determine which competencies to develop internally and which to source externally, focusing internal efforts on areas that provide unique competitive advantages while leveraging partnerships to cover niche or highly technical needs.

Future development priorities should be aligned with WP5 market intelligence and client feedback, focusing on emerging regulatory requirements and high-demand use cases. These strategic actions will inform regular updates to the TEF service offer roadmap and guide stakeholder engagement, ensuring the consortium remains agile, competitive, and capable of meeting evolving cybersecurity challenges in the conformity assessment market.

5. Conclusion

This deliverable has provided an **in-depth exploration of the regulatory landscape relevant to AI-based and robotics solutions**, including major frameworks such as the AI Act, Data Act, and Cybersecurity Act. It has also identified associated standards, both harmonized and non-harmonized, and categorized them according to thematic requirements. This structured approach enables project partners, who specialize in testing, to align their services with evolving compliance expectations.

The **regulatory frameworks explored in this document are** dynamic and still evolving, particularly in the case of the AI Act and Data Act. While these regulations lack stable references, this deliverable has proposed valuable pointers through standards and technical guides, which can serve as a foundation for developing conformity assessment services tailored to AI technologies. However, it is important to note that **many regulations and standards were** not initially designed for AI-specific applications, **requiring further adaptation and analysis** to address the unique risks and complexities these systems present.

This deliverable has also provided examples of best practices, covering phases from contracting to post-delivery processes. These recommendations serve as a reference for partners to consider when implementing conformity assessment services. They offer insights into **aspects that differ significantly from traditional testing services**, illustrating key considerations and sharing experiences to guide the successful delivery of such specialized services.

Looking forward, continuous learning and adaptation **remain critical to staying ahead of regulatory changes**. By reflecting on lessons learned, incorporating feedback into methodologies and deeply understanding our current capabilities and gaps to fill, project partners can refine their processes and enhance the quality and relevance of their services. **Future work will focus on elaborating additional content and support materials to assist partners** already offering conformity assessment services in expanding their scope. Additionally, efforts will be made to guide and support other partners interested in establishing such services, providing them with the necessary frameworks and insights to navigate this complex landscape. WP3 ultimately aims to support these partners in navigating regulatory complexities and contributing to the development of robust, reliable, and forward-looking services in the rapidly evolving field of AI.

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6.8. Data Act

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- **EU Cloud Code of Conduct (CoC) Certification** - Certification for compliance with EU cloud computing regulations. <https://eucoc.cloud/en/home>
- **GO-FAIR Principles** - Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable principles for data management and stewardship. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
- **GDPR Certification**. Example of a label: <https://euoprivacy.org/fr>

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